

Annex 3

Stakeholder workshop agenda and worksheets

This annex contains a draft of the workshop agenda. The workshop is a structured, deliberative process that operationalises the research questions.

The research questions to be answered in the workshop are:

RQ1: What is the current state of knowledge, regulation, and practice regarding Open Science and GenAI in scientific exchange?

RQ2: What opportunities, challenges, and emerging trends can be identified in this domain (STEEPED lens)?

RQ3: How do key stakeholders envision possible futures involving GenAI and Open Science in Europe?

RQ4: What risks and safeguards should be considered for MEPs and committees (ITRE/IMCO/CULT), and how are these assessed using likelihood-by-impact scoring and linked explicitly to scenarios and time horizons?

RQ5: What policy options and political measures should be initiated now for each scenario to balance innovation and progress with trustworthy research?

The workshop is planned as follows:

Workshop Agenda (120 minutes)

0:00–0:04 | Welcome + ground rules

Purpose, EP lens (ITRE/IMCO/CULT), timeboxing.

0:04–0:08 | Lightning scenario reads

30–45 sec each; participants note implied logic + hinted risks.

0:08–0:20 | Study framing

State of play OS×GenAI (RQ1), STEEPED opportunities/challenges (RQ2), why scenarios (RQ3), what the EP needs (RQ4–RQ5).

0:20–0:28 | Cluster check (plenary)

Validate/adjust the four scenario clusters; lock assignments.

0:28–0:56 | Breakouts: Exercise A (Cluster Profile)

Core logic, early indicators, top risks with scenario quotes.

0:56–1:16 | Breakouts: Exercise B (Risk Register)

Select 2–3 systemic risks; add likelihood/impact, time horizon, EP relevance.

1:16–1:32 | Plenary: Exercise C (Pitch + scoring)

60–90 sec/group; score likelihood then impact; select Top 5 most likely risks.

1:32–1:55 | Exercise D (Countermeasures)

Design policy options for Top 5 (quadruple helix + EP levers).

1:55–2:00 | Wrap

One key insight + one actionable EP measure.

Workshop Exercise Sheet — Open Science × GenAI (Participant)

Participant name: _____

Cluster group (A–D): _____

Mode: On-site / Online

Quick notes during lightning reads

- Signals/phrases that stood out: 1. 2.
- Risks hinted by scenarios: 1. 2.

Exercise A) Cluster Profile Block (fill in with your group)

A1. Cluster working title

A2. Core logic of the future of scientific exchange (3–5 sentences)

(Describe how scientific exchange is produced/validated/shared, what changes structurally, and what becomes “normal”.)

A3. Early indicators (2027–2030) — max 8 bullets

- 1.
- 2.
- 3.
- 4.
- 5.
- 6.
- 7.
- 8.

A4. Risks in relation to the scientific exchange (up to 5) — include scenario quote + description

(Use short, verbatim phrases from the scenarios of your cluster as evidence. Keep quote brief.)

Risk (short label)	Quote from scenario (evidence)	Risk description (what can go wrong, for whom, why)
1	“...”	

2	“ ... ”	
3	“ ... ”	
4	“ ... ”	
5	“ ... ”	

Exercise B) Risk Register Block (2–3 systemic risks for your cluster)

Instruction: Select **2–3 systemic risks** from Exercise A. Together with your group, **copy/paste** the risk label + quote + description into a collaborative digital working space. Your moderator will give you the link.

Exercise C) Plenary scoring (Top 5 “most likely to appear” risks)

Instruction: In plenary, we will score all proposed systemic risks. We will then pick the **Top 5 most likely** (highest Likelihood; tie-breaker = Impact; second tie-breaker = EP relevance). Record the selected Top 5 here.

Top 5 risks (final selection)	Cluster	Likelihood (1–5)	Impact (1–5)	Notes (why it’s likely / where it shows up first)
1				
2				
3				
4				
5				

Exercise D) Countermeasures for the Top 5 risks

Instruction: For each of the Top 5 risks (see last table), define **measures to initiate now** and later. Focus on realistic, implementable actions and note the European Parliament's levers.

D-table

1 Risk: _____

Domain	Measures to initiate now (0–12 months)	Measures to build/scale (1–3 years)	Owner(s) / implementers	EP lever (legislation / budget / oversight / convening)
Scientific Exchange				

2 Risk: _____

Domain	Measures to initiate now (0–12 months)	Measures to build/scale (1–3 years)	Owner(s) / implementers	EP lever (legislation / budget / oversight / convening)
Scientific Exchange				

3 Risk: _____

Domain	Measures to initiate now (0–12 months)	Measures to build/scale (1–3 years)	Owner(s) / implementers	EP lever (legislation / budget / oversight / convening)
Scientific Exchange				

4 Risk: _____

Domain	Measures to initiate now (0–12 months)	Measures to build/scale (1–3 years)	Owner(s) / implementers	EP lever (legislation / budget / oversight / convening)
Scientific Exchange				

5 Risk: _____

Domain	Measures to initiate now (0–12 months)	Measures to build/scale (1–3 years)	Owner(s) / implementers	EP lever (legislation / budget / oversight / convening)
Scientific Exchange				